

Variability in yield and yield components under normal and late sowings. Malda, West Bengal, India, 1985-86.

Sowing date	Line	Duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Panicle length (cm)	Tillers (no.)	Grains/panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Sterility (%)
13 Jul	CN657-21	106	161	21	8	120	28	2.5	19
	CN671-28	111	149	24	7	173	25	2.8	18
	CN671-29	102	131	23	10	145	30	2.6	20
	Mean	106	147	23	8	146	27.6	2.6	19
10 Aug	CN657-21	92	137	23	11	122	29	1.5	19
	CN671-28	101	121	23	9	127	28	1.5	23
	CN671-29	87	98	22	13	103	29	1.8	24
	Mean	93	119	23	11	117	28.6	1.6	22
	% reduction	12.3	19.0	0.0	-37.5	19.8	-3.6	38.46	
<i>F</i> value ^a	Variety (V)	180.4**	81.05**	0.07 ns	6.83**	130.5**	34.4**	0.84 ns	
	Sowing (S)	635.2**	39.23**	0.014 ns	12.61**	303.6**	9.4**	6.55**	
	V × S	11.9**	1.3 ns	0.019 ns	0.46 ns	95.72**	19.1**	0.34 ns	

^a ** = significant at the 1% level.

varieties.

Late-planted rice generally encounters two environmental factors that can reduce yield: a gradual decline in average night/day temperatures and drought during the reproductive stage. The effects are pronounced in northern West Bengal.

We conducted an experiment in the old Gangetic alluvium region at Malda (25°33'N) to identify important characters for late sowing and to evaluate the effect of temperature on the reproductive stage.

Three advanced lines derived from CNL 231/Pankaj and Pankalash/CRI006 crosses were sown on 13 Jul and 10 Aug. The 30-d-old seedlings were transplanted 20 × 15 cm apart in 5-m² plots with 5 replications. Fertilizer was applied 60-30-30 kg NPK/ha.

In the variability study, heading duration, total grains/panicle, and 1,000-grain weight significantly differed among varieties and by sowing date, and variety × sowing interaction (see table). Although plant height, filled

grains/panicle, and yield were reduced by 19, 19.8, and 38.5% in late sown rices, effective tiller numbers and 1,000-grain weight increased.

Days to heading was 102-111 in the Jul-sown crop and 87-101 in the Aug-sown crop. Average temperature was 26.5°C during panicle initiation for Jul and 23.3°C for Aug sowings. Average temperatures of 22°C and 20°C prevailed during grain filling.

Although low temperatures were not critical for mid-Aug sowing, sterility % was higher with late sowing. □

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization

DROUGHT TOLERANCE

Drought tolerance of some rice hybrids and their parents

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In several crop plants, hybrids have shown higher drought tolerance than their parents. This has been attributed to deeper and more developed root systems. Under such situations as midseason rain failures in rainfed rice, this capacity could make the difference between a relatively good crop and a total failure.

We evaluated 11 rice hybrids and their parents for drought tolerance in a split-plot design in 2 replications using 15 plants each during the 1984 dry season. Irrigation treatments were in main plots and the hybrids and their parents in subplots. Irrigation was withheld for 14 d at late tillering or panicle initiation. Plots were normally irrigated afterwards. The mean values and percent reduction of four traits under normal irrigation and under drought stress are presented in the table.

Grain yield reduction in five hybrids was less than in the lesser affected parent. In another five hybrids, it was between the two parents. Only one hybrid had higher yield reduction than

both parents, probably because this hybrid flowered in late May and was affected by hot winds.

Among the parents, Taichung Senyu 285 had exceptionally high tolerance for drought, with higher yield under stress than all the other hybrids. None of the correlation coefficients between characters were significant. □

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Grain yield reduction and some yield components of hybrids and their parents under irrigated and drought conditions. Raipur, India, 1984 dry season.

Entry	Situation ^a	Plant height		Effective tillers		Filled grains/panicle		Grain yield/plant	
		Mean (cm)	Reduction (%)	Mean (no.)	Reduction (%)	Mean (no.)	Reduction (%)	Mean (g)	Reduction (%)
BG367-4/MW10	N	72.4	16.8	15.2	7.2	63.6	23.4	15.2	7.2
	D	60.2		14.1		48.7		14.1	
IR25571-31/MW10	N	61.0	1.6	15.0	33.3	77.3	21.1	15.0	14.0
	D	60.0		10.0		61.0		12.9	
MW10/Samridhi	N	74.0	23.8	13.6	1.5	74.0	52.3	13.6	9.6
	D	56.4		13.4		35.3		12.3	
IR36/Azucena	N	60.0	12.3	13.3	4.5	94.0	33.1	13.3	14.3
	D	52.6		12.7		62.9		11.4	
IR9752-71/Ratna	N	60.0	9.3	10.0	28.0	60.4	23.2	11.0	12.7
	D	54.4		7.2		46.4		9.6	
Taichung Senyu 285/Samridhi	N	12.4	21.0	15.5	1.9	73.0	8.5	15.5	16.1
	D	57.2		15.2		66.8		13.0	
Taichung Senyu 285/MW10	N	75.0	21.7	16.3	1.8	75.0	52.2	16.2	4.3
	D	58.7		16.0		35.8		15.5	
RP1140-27/Ratna	N	60.6	17.0	15.3	20.3	70.3	15.5	18.5	13.5
	D	50.5		12.2		59.4		16.0	
IR13240-82/IR36	N	75.0	13.2	14.3	14.0	71.5	59.2	14.5	42.7
	D	65.1		12.3		29.2		8.3	
IR25571-31/Poorva	N	77.7	13.1	11.2	9.8	77.8	23.1	16.0	26.3
	D	61.5		10.1		59.8		11.8	
Taichung Senyu 285/Poorva	N	65.0	16.5	15.0	26.0	69.0	56.9	15.0	38.0
	D	54.3		11.1		29.7		9.3	
MW10	N	71.2	17.7	12.0	9.2	77.2	9.1	16.6	20.5
	D	58.4		10.9		70.2		13.2	
BG367-4	N	72.2	22.3	12.0	5.8	75.0	68.0	9.4	24.5
	D	56.1		11.3		24.0		7.7	
IR25571-31	N	73.4	14.7	17.0	27.1	73.4	45.6	13.8	31.9
	D	62.6		12.4		39.2		9.4	
Samridhi	N	76.6	27.9	19.0	27.4	76.6	42.2	18.4	58.1
	D	55.2		13.8		44.3		7.7	
IR36	N	72.0	23.5	19.0	16.3	72.0	42.8	13.6	57.3
	D	55.1		15.9		41.2		5.8	
Azucena	N	62.3	12.8	7.0	17.1	62.3	32.9	9.7	18.6
	D	54.3		5.8		41.8		7.9	
IR9752-71	N	60.4	7.1	23.0	29.1	60.4	54.3	17.6	30.7
	D	56.1		16.3		27.6		12.2	
Ratna	N	74.0	17.8	16.0	14.4	74.0	29.7	16.2	45.1
	D	60.8		13.7		52.0		8.9	
Taichung Senyu 285	N	66.2	19.3	17.0	8.8	66.2	50.0	18.6	3.8
	D	53.4		15.5		32.8		17.9	
Poorva	N	67.8	8.1	21.0	34.3	75.6	17.2	19.2	14.6
	D	62.3		13.8		62.6		16.4	
RP1140-27	N	68.2	15.2	16.0	25.0	69.0	43.3	13.2	8.3
	D	57.8		12.0		39.1		12.1	
IR13240-32	N	63.2	25.0	25.0	22.0	69.0	43.3	19.2	32.8
	D	47.4		19.5		39.1		12.9	
LSD (0.05)									
Main plot means		0.4		0.5		2.5		0.8	
Subplot means		2.3		1.7		2.8		1.3	
Subplots at same main plot level		3.3		2.4		3.9		1.8	

^aN = normal, D = drought.

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